

SPAM EMAIL DETECTION WITH MACHINE LEARNING ENHANCED BY BIO-INSPIRED METAHEURISTIC ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

Electronic mail has eased communication methods for many organisations as well as individuals. This method is exploited for fraudulent gain by spammers through sending unsolicited emails. This article aims to present a method for detection of spam emails with machine learning algorithms that are optimized with bio-inspired methods. A literature review is carried to explore the efficient methods applied on different datasets to achieve good results. An extensive research was done to implement machine learning models using Naïve Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Decision Tree and Multi-Layer Perceptron on seven different email datasets, along with feature extraction and pre-processing. The bio-inspired algorithms like Particle Swarm Optimization and Genetic Algorithm were implemented to optimize the performance of classifiers. Multinomial Naïve Bayes with Genetic Algorithm performed the best overall. The comparison of our results with other machine learning and bio-inspired models to show the best suitable model is also discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning models have been utilized for multiple purposes in the field of computer science from resolving a network traffic issue to detecting a malware. Emails

are used regularly by many people for communication and for socialising. Security breaches that compromises customer data allows ‘spammers’ to spoof a compromised email address to send illegitimate (spam) emails. This is also exploited to gain unauthorized access to their device by tricking the user into clicking the spam link within the spam email, that constitutes a phishing attack [1].

Many tools and techniques are offered by companies in order to detect spam emails in a network. Organisations have set up filtering mechanisms to detect unsolicited emails by setting up rules and configuring the firewall settings. Google is one of the top companies that offers 99.9% success in detecting such emails [2]. There are different areas for deploying the spam filters such as on the gate way (router), on the cloud hosted applications or on the user’s computer. In order to overcome the detection problem of spam emails, methods such as content-based filtering, rule-based filtering or Bayesian filtering have been applied.

Unlike the ‘knowledge engineering’ where spam detection rules are set up and are in constant need of manual updating thus consuming time and resources, Machine learning makes it easier because it learns to

recognise the unsolicited emails (spam) and legitimate emails (ham) automatically and then applies those learned instructions to unknown incoming emails [2].

Detection of spam is important for securing message and e-mail communication. The most common technique for spam detection is the utilization of Naïve Bayesian method and features sets that assess the presence of spam keywords [17],[18],[19]. Detecting phishing emails[20],[21].

The proposed spam detection to resolve the issue of the spam classification problem can be further experimented by feature selection or automated parameter selection for the models. This research conducts experiments involving five different machine learning models with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA). This will be compared with the base models to conclude whether the proposed models have improved the performance with parameter tuning.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

"A support vector machine based Naive Bayes algorithm for spam filtering"

Naive Bayes classifiers are widely used to filter spam emails, however, the strong independence assumptions between features limit their performance in accurately identifying spams. To address this issue, we proposed a support machine vector based naive Bayes - SVM-NB - filtering system. The SVM-NB first constructs an optimal separating hyperplane that divides samples in the training set into two categories. For samples located nearby the hyperplane, if they are in different categories, one of them

will be eliminated from the training set. In this way, the dependence between samples is reduced and the entire training sample space is simplified. With the trimmed training set, the naive Bayes algorithm is applied to classify emails in the test set. The SVM-NB system is evaluated with the dataset obtained from DATAMALL. Experiment results demonstrate that SVM-NB can achieve a higher spam-detection accuracy and a faster classification speed.

"Machine learning for email spam filtering: Review approaches and open research problems"

The upsurge in the volume of unwanted emails called spam has created an intense need for the development of more dependable and robust antispam filters. Machine learning methods of recent are being used to successfully detect and filter spam emails. We present a systematic review of some of the popular machine learning based email spam filtering approaches. Our review covers survey of the important concepts, attempts, efficiency, and the research trend in spam filtering. The preliminary discussion in the study background examines the applications of machine learning techniques to the email spam filtering process of the leading internet service providers (ISPs) like Gmail, Yahoo and Outlook emails spam filters. Discussion on general email spam filtering process, and the various efforts by different researchers in combating spam through the use machine learning techniques was done. Our review compares the strengths and drawbacks of existing machine learning approaches and the open research problems in spam filtering. We recommended deep leaning

and deep adversarial learning as the future techniques that can effectively handle the menace of spam emails.

"Machine learning methods for spam E-Mail classification",

The increasing volume of unsolicited bulk e-mail (also known as spam) has generated a need for reliable anti-spam filters. Machine learning techniques now days used to automatically filter the spam e-mail in a very successful rate. In this paper we review some of the most popular machine learning methods (Bayesian classification, k-NN, ANNs, SVMs, Artificial immune system and Rough sets) and of their applicability to the problem of spam Email classification. Descriptions of the algorithms are presented, and the comparison of their performance on the SpamAssassin spam corpus is presented.

"Hybrid decision tree and logistic regression classifier for email spam detection",

Email spam is an increasing problem because it disrupting and time consuming for user, since the easy and cheap of sending email. Email Spam filtering can be done with a binary classification with machine learning as classifier. To date, email spam detection still challenging since the email spam still happens a lot and the detection still need improvement. Decision Tree (DT) is one of famous classifier since DT able to handle nominal and numerical attributes and increasing the efficiency of computing. However, DT has a weakness in over-sensitivity to the training set and the noise data or instance that can degrade the performance. In this study, we propose hybrid combination Logistic Regression (LR) and DT for email spam detection. LR

is used for reduce noisy data or instance before data feed to DT induction. Noisy data reducing is done by LR by filtering correct prediction with certain false negative threshold. In this study, Spambase dataset is used to evaluate the proposed method. From the experiment, the result shows that proposed method yield impressive and promising result with the accuracy is 91.67%. It can be concluded that LR able to improve DT performance by reducing noisy data.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

- ❖ Feng *et al.* [1] describes a hybrid system between two machine learning algorithms i.e. SVM-NB. Their proposed method is to apply the SVM algorithm and generate the hyperplane between the given dimensions and reduce the training set by eliminating datapoints. This set will then be implemented with NB algorithm to predict the probability of the outcome. This experiment was conducted on Chinese text corpus. They successfully implemented their proposed algorithm and there was an increase in accuracy when compared to NB and SVM on their own.
- ❖ Mohammed *et al.* [4] aimed to detect the unsolicited emails by experimenting with different classifiers such as: NB, SVM, KNN, Tree and Rule based algorithms. They generated a vocabulary of Spam and Ham emails which is then

used to filter through the training and testing data. Their experiment was conducted with Python programming language on Email-1431 dataset. They concluded that NB was the best working classifier followed by Support Vector Machine.

- ❖ Wijaya and Bisri [5] proposes a hybrid-based algorithm, which is integrating Decision Tree with Logistic Regression along with False Negative threshold. They were successful in increasing the performance of DT. The results were compared with the prior research. The experiment was conducted on the SpamBase dataset. The proposed method presented a 91.67 accuracy.
- ❖ Belkebir and Guessoum [7] reviewed the SVM algorithm along with Bee Swarm Optimization (BSO) and Chi-Squared on Arabic Text. Since there have been plenty of research conducted for text mining on English and some European languages, the authors considered to review the algorithms work on Arabic language. They experimented with three different approaches to categorise automatic text _ Neural networks, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and SVM optimizing with Bee Swarm Algorithm (BSO) along with Chi-Squared. Bee Swarming Optimization algorithm is inspired by the behavior of swarm of bees to achieve global solution. A search

area is divided and each area within the divided section is assigned to other bees to explore. Every solution is distributed amongst the bees and the best solution is accepted and the process is repeated until the solution meet the criteria of the problem.

Disadvantages

- In the existing work, the system is not accurate on large data sets due to lack of bio-inspired algorithms.
- This system is less performance due to lack of accurate spam detection on large set of emails.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed spam detection to resolve the issue of the spam classification problem can be further experimented by feature selection or automated parameter selection for the models. This research conducts experiments involving five different machine learning models with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA). This will be compared with the base models to conclude whether the proposed models have improved the performance with parameter tuning.

- 1) To explore machine learning algorithms for the spam detection problem.
- 2) To investigate the workings of the algorithms with the acquired datasets.
- 3) To implement the bio-inspired algorithms.
- 4) To test and compare the accuracy of base models with bio-inspired implementation.
- 5) To implement the framework using Python.

Advantages

- ❖ The proposed spam detection to resolve the issue of the spam classification problem can be further experimented by feature selection or automated parameter selection for the models.
- ❖ The system is more effective since spam detection problem is solving by GADT proposed algorithm.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

6. IMPLEMENTATION

MODULES:

1. DATASET

The dataset has been divided into a training set and testing set. Both the training set and the testing set contain emails without header and emails with header. In this paper, we only focus on email data with the header. Due to the irrationality of the segmentation of the training set and the testing set in the original dataset, after merging the two datasets, the training-validation set and the testing set are redivided. The dataset is divided by stratified random sampling; that is, random samples are taken from

legitimate email and phishing email at the same proportion. This ensures that the two datasets used in training and testing phases are well.

2.USER QUERIES

Users can have queries about the process. This part of project is dedicated to make and get response for queries that are needed to answerable. The major part of the modules is making project as interactive one, queries have been very normally arise to users regarding different details about the process.

3.GRAPH ANALYSIS

Graph analysis is the part where admin can knows the statistics about process of details. The data are taken from the project flow and it shows until updated value. The data are gives clear solution to admin that part of improvement and user satisfaction and other factors.

4.ANALYSIS

analysis of email structure. a circle represents a character, and a rectangle represents a word. A rectangle is filled with an indefinite number of circles, indicating that the word consists of an indefinite number of characters.

7. CONCLUSION

We use a new deep learning model named to detect phishing emails. The model employs an improved RCNN to model the email header and the email body at both the character level and the word level. Therefore, the noise is introduced into the model minimally. In the model, we use the attention mechanism in the header and the

body, making the model pay more attention to the more valuable information between them. We use the unbalanced dataset closer to the real-world situation to conduct experiments and evaluate the model. The model obtains a promising result. Several experiments are performed to demonstrate the benefits of the proposed model.

8. FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

For future work, we will focus on how to improve our model for detecting phishing emails with no email header and only an email body.

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